

Rapid expansion of the Oak lace bug *Corythucha arcuata* (Say, 1832) (Hemiptera: Tingidae) in Bulgaria

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Abstract: New records, host associations, damages on oaks and the potential threat of alien oak lace bug (*Corythucha arcuata*) to native forests in Bulgaria are reported and briefly discussed.

Key words: *Corythucha arcuata*, host plants, new localities, spreading

Introduction

The oak lace bug, *Corythucha arcuata* (Say, 1832) (Heteroptera: Tingidae), is of North American origin and is widely distributed in the United States of America and the southern part of Canada. It is an invasive species in Europe and has been firstly recorded in Italy (Bernardinelli & Zandigiacomo, 2000) and Switzerland (Forster et al., 2005). *Corythucha arcuata* has spread to a large part of Turkey (Mutun et al., 2009) and it was expected the alien species to reach Bulgaria in a short time (Simov et al., 2012). In 2012, the oak lace bug was found for the first time on the Balkan Peninsula in Plovdiv City and Zlati dol Vill. near the town of Simeonovgrad (Dobrev et al., 2013). In the next few years, the species penetrated in many regions of the country (Georgiev et al., 2017).

The present paper is a continuation of a previous study of alien true bugs in Bulgaria and summarizes data on the rapid expansion of *C. arcuata* in the country.

Materials and Methods

The field studies were conducted in the period 2015-2017. Many visual observations of infested oak trees were performed within the ESENIAS-TOOLS and TUNESinURB project activities. The biological material was collected using an entomological beating sheet and by hand – after searching leaves of infested host trees or hibernating places in bark crevices or under tree bark. Damages, adult insects, nymphs and eggs were photographed with a Panasonic Lumix DMC-FZ200 and Olympus E-30 cameras.

Results and Discussion

During the study period, *C. arcuata* was observed in many new localities in Bulgaria.

Material examined: Burgas District: Primorsko Town, 26 m a.s.l., 42.24620°N, 027.75087°E, host *Quercus frainetto* Ten., *Q. hartwissiana* Steven, *Q. cerris* L., 08.10.2016, G.

Georgiev, P. Mirchev, M. Georgieva obs.; Kiten Town, 34 m a.s.l., 42.23610°N, 027.77933°E, host *Q. frainetto*, 09.10.2016, G. Georgiev, P. Mirchev, M. Georgieva obs.; Malko Tarnovo Town, 337 m a.s.l., 41.97931°N, 027.53238°E, host *Q. frainetto*, *Q. hartwissiana*, *Q. cerris*, 10.10.2016, G. Georgiev, P. Mirchev, M. Georgieva obs.; Brashlyan Vill., 240 m a.s.l., 42.045659°N, 027.426628°E, host *Q. polycarpa* Schur, 08.08.2016, S. Grozeva obs.; **Haskovo District:** Simeonovgrad Town, 89 m a.s.l., 42.0312°N, 025.8265°E, host *Q. robur* L., 26.06.2016, S. Grozeva leg.; near Simeonovgrad Town., 99 m a.s.l., 42.048243°N, 025.872616°E, host *Q. robur*, 20.11.2015, S. Grozeva leg.; Svilengrad Town, 58 m a.s.l., 41.774558°N, 026.145344°E, host *Q. robur*, 27.06.2016, S. Grozeva leg.; Harmanli Town, 75 m a.s.l., 41.89095°N, 025.965609°E, host *Q. robur*, 27.06.2016, S. Grozeva leg.; west of Brod Vill., 140 m a.s.l., 42.063854°N, 025.66100°E, host *Q. robur*, *Q. petraea* (Matt.) Liebl., 21.06.2016, N. Simov obs.; **Kardzhali District:** Kardzhali Town, 275 m a.s.l., 41.38371°N, 025.22406°E, host *Q. cerris*, *Q. petraea*, 18.08.2016, G. Georgiev, P. Mirchev, M. Georgieva obs.; **Yambol District:** Topolovgrad Town, 320 m a.s.l., 42.077351°N, 026.324859°E, host *Quercus* sp., 08.08.2016, G. Georgiev, P. Mirchev, M. Georgieva obs.; **Sliven District:** Sliven Town – park in the town, 243 m a.s.l., 42.680516°N, 026.317874°E, host *Q. robur* L., 30.08.2015, S. Grozeva leg.; **Stara Zagora District:** north of Gurkovo Town, 310 m a.s.l., 42.66050°N, 025.77243°E, host *Q. cerris*, 27.10.2015, N. Simov obs.; east of Nikolaevo Vill., 285 m a.s.l., 42.630158°N, 025.829975°E, host *Q. cerris*, *Q. robur*, 27.10.2015, N. Simov obs.; Zhrebchevo Dam, 287 m a.s.l., 42.57736°N, 025.88972°E, host *Q. frainetto*, 27.10.2015, N. Simov obs.; **Plovdiv District:** Manole Vill., 157 m a.s.l., 42.10096°N, 024.55540°E, host *Q. robur*, 10.06.2016, G. Georgiev, P. Mirchev, M. Georgieva obs.; Kalekovets Vill., 179 m a.s.l., 42.14202°N, 024.49163°E, host *Q. robur*, 15.07.2016, G. Georgiev, P. Mirchev, M. Georgieva obs.; Trilistnik

Vill., 166 m a.s.l., 42.12167°N, 024.52228°E, host *Q. robur*, *Castanea sativa* Mill., 15.07.2016, G. Georgiev, P. Mirchev, M. Georgieva obs.; Trilistnik Vill., 161 m a.s.l., 42.22228°N, 024.86248°E, host *Q. pedunculiflora* K.Koch, 27.07.2016, N. Simov, M. Langourov, R. Bekchiev obs.; Plovdiv Town, Greben Chanel, 165 m a.s.l., 42.143472°N, 024.71014°E, host *Q. robur*, 06.08.2016, S. Grozeva obs.; Plovdiv Town, Bunardzhika Hill, 180 m a.s.l., 42.146104°N, 024.740166°E, host *Q. robur*, 06.08.2016, S. Grozeva obs.; **Blagoevgrad District:** Sandanski Town, 262 m a.s.l., 41.34194°N, 023.17061°E, host *Q. petraea*, 28.08.2016, G. Georgiev, P. Mirchev, M. Georgieva obs.; Gotse Delchev Town, 538 m a.s.l., 41.34227°N, 023.44058°E, host *Q. pubescens* Willd., *Q. robur*, 29.08.2016, G. Georgiev, P. Mirchev, M. Georgieva obs.; Gotse Delchev Town, Park in the center of the town, 510 m a.s.l., 41.573392°N, 023.736502°E, host *Q. pubescens*, *Q. robur*, 16.10.2015, S. Grozeva obs.; *ibid.*, 02.07.2016, N. Simov obs.; west of Blatska Vill., 516 m a.s.l., 41.536184°N, 023.876637°E, host *Q. pubescens*, 03.08.2015, N. Simov obs.; **Sofia District:** Sofia City, 550 m a.s.l., 42.694398°N, 023.336582°E, host *Q. robur*, 01.06.2017, N. Simov obs.; Sofia City, 550 m a.s.l., 42.685744°N, 023.335938°E, host *Q. robur*, 21.06.2017, S. Grozeva obs.; Sofia City, 556 m a.s.l., 42.694707°N, 023.33667°E, host *Q. robur*, 11.09.2016, S. Grozeva obs.; Sofia City, 556 m a.s.l., 42.694697°N, 023.33667°E, host *Q. robur*, 11.11.2017, N. Simov obs.; **Pleven District:** near Koilovtsi Vill., 177 m a.s.l., 43.48032°N, 024.73766°E, host *Q. robur*, 23.10.2015, N. Simov obs.; Belene Town, 26 m a.s.l., 43.64133°N, 025.12346°E, host *Quercus* sp., 24.10.2015, N. Simov obs.; **Ruse District:** west of Obretenik Vill., 161 m a.s.l., 43.57083°N, 025.75651°E, host *Q. robur*, *Q. frainetto*, 26.10.2015, N. Simov obs.; Ivanovo Vill., 117 m a.s.l., 43.69156°N, 025.95144°E, host *Q. cerris*, 26.10.2015, N. Simov obs.; Batakliata hunting area, 200 m a.s.l., 43.64582°N, 026.11861°E, host *Q. cerris*, *Q. robur*, 26.10.2015, N. Simov obs.; **Veliko Tarnovo District:** east of Polski Trumbesh Vill., 37 m a.s.l.,

Table 1. Host plants of *Corythucha arcuata* in Bulgaria

Common hosts with massively found symptoms	Hosts with restricted distribution in Bulgaria	Occasional hosts
<i>Quercus robur</i> L.	<i>Castanea sativa</i> Mill.	<i>Lysimachia punctata</i> L.
<i>Quercus petraea</i> (Matt.) Liebl.		<i>Rosa canina</i> L.
<i>Quercus pubescens</i> Willd.		<i>Rubus caesius</i> L.
<i>Quercus cerris</i> L.		<i>Rubus</i> sp.
<i>Quercus frainetto</i> Ten.		<i>Acer platanoides</i> L.
<i>Quercus hartwissiana</i> Steven		
<i>Quercus pedunculiflora</i> K.Koch		
<i>Quercus polycarpa</i> Schur		

Fig. 1. Recorded localities of *Corythucha arcuata* in Bulgaria. Semicircles – first records in 2012, black circles – new records 2015-2017.

43.37957°N, 025.65186°E, host *Q. robur*, 27.10.2015, N. Simov obs.; Gorsko Kalugerovo Vill., 200 m a.s.l., 43.111531°N, 025.274208°E, host *Q. robur*, 25.06.2016, S. Grozeva obs.; Momin sbor Vill., 220 m a.s.l., 43.087834° N, 025.496340°E, host *Q. robur*, 25.06.2016, S. Grozeva obs.; Voneshta Voda Vill., 420 m a.s.l., 42.876428°N, 025.637565°E, host *Q. robur*, 25.06.2016, S. Grozeva obs.; Voneshta Voda Vill., 410 m a.s.l., 42.876216°N, 25.637647°E, host *Q. robur*, 01.09.2015, S. Grozeva obs.; Voneshta Voda Vill., 401 m a.s.l., 42.87836°N, 25.64047°E, host *Q. robur*, *Lysimachia punctata* L., *Rosa canina* L., *Rubus caesius* L., 27.10.2015, N. Simov obs.; **Sevlievo District:** south of Dobromirka Vill., 385 m a.s.l., 43.061900°N, 025.286349°E, host *Q. robur*, 17.08.2016, N. Simov obs.; **Razgrad District:** Loznitsa Vill., 220 m a.s.l., 43.362905°N, 026.605182°E, host *Q. cerris*, 02.08.2017, N. Simov obs.

The localities of the oak lace bug in Bulgaria (Fig. 1) are situated in the lowland and hill zone of the country, in the belt of xerothermic oak forests up to 600-700 m a.s.l.

In this study, 14 tree, shrub and herbaceous species were detected as common or occasional hosts of *C. arcuata* in Bulgaria (Table 1). Besides eight

Quercus species (Fig. 2A), the oak lace bug was also established to develop on sweet chestnut, *Castanea sativa* (Fig. 2B). During hibernation, the species was found under bark and in bark crevices of *Q. robur* and *Pinus sylvestris* L. Among the occasional hosts of the species in Bulgaria, *Lysimachia punctata*, *Rosa canina*, *Acer platanoides* and *Rubus caesius* (Fig. 2C) were recorded. In Slovenia, *C. arcuata* was also found on other host plants: *Malus sylvestris* and *Ulmus* spp. (Jurc & Jurc, 2017).

Five years after the first record on the Balkan Peninsula, the oak lace bug has invaded most of Bulgaria. The species has spread rapidly, occupying urban areas and oak forests in the country. In the case of heavy infestation, the oak trees turn yellow in the middle of the summer and lose their leaves earlier than usual (Fig. 2D). In heavy attacked trees in mid-July about all of the leaves suffer damage due to *C. arcuata* feeding activity. About 85% of the leaves display discoloration, that can be spread over half of the leaf surface (Fig. 2E). The high population density of the oak lace bug appears to be the major threat to the native sucking insects in oak forests, such as honeydew producers, especially in the Strandzha Mt. (Georgiev et al., 2008). *Corythucha arcuata* causes

Fig. 2. Host plants of *Corythucha arcuata* in Bulgaria and impact on them: A – *C. arcuata* on *Quercus robur*; B – *C. arcuata* on *Castanea sativa*; C – *C. arcuata* on *Rubus caesius*; D – Strongly damaged *Q. pedunculiflora* stand in the beginning of July; E – heavy leaf discoloration due to *C. arcuata* feeding activity; F – strongly attacked solitary *Q. robur* trees; G – strongly attacked solitary *Q. fainetto* trees; I, J – strongly attacked one-year-old oak seedlings.

strong damages to oak trees in urban green infrastructure, as well (Fig. 2F). In forest stands, the highly attacked young oak seedlings are particularly threatened (Fig. 2I, J). *Castanea sativa* in the Belasitsa Mt. has not yet been attacked by the pest. However, the chestnut stands in the region are in poor health condition due to the negative impact of *Cryphonectria parasitica* (Murrill.) Barr. (Georgieva et al., 2013) and, therefore, are potentially threatened during future calamities of *C. arcuata*.

The expansion of the oak lace bug is already registered in Turkey (Mutun, 2003; Mutun et al., 2009; Küçükbasmacı, 2014), Croatia (Hrašovec et al., 2013; Nikl, 2017), Serbia (Pap et al., 2015), Romania (Chireceanu et al., 2017), Slovenia (Jurc & Jurc, 2017), Hungary (Csepelényi et al., 2017a, b) and

Russia (Neimorovats et al., 2017). Almost all of our records are close to the main European roads E-80, E-79, E-85, E-87, and this fact supports our hypothesis of human mediated dispersal mechanism of oak and sycamore lace bugs in Bulgaria as stowaways (Simov et al., 2012; Dobрева et al., 2013).

Acknowledgments: The study was supported by the Financial Mechanism of the European Economic Area (2009-2014), Programme BG03 Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services: Project 'East and South European Network for Invasive Alien Species – A tool to support the management of alien species in Bulgaria' (ESENIASTOOLS), D-33-51/30.06.2015; Project 'Improving the Bulgarian Biodiversity Information System' (IBBIS), D-33-72/20.07.2015; Project 'Toward better understanding of ecosystem services in urban environment through evaluation and mapping of ecosystem services, (TUNESinURB), D-33-82/14.08.2015.

References

- Bernardinelli I., Zandigiacomo P. 2000 Prima segnalazione di *Corythucha arcuata* (Say) (Heteroptera, Tingidae) in Europa. *Informatore Fitopatologico* 50: 47-49.
- Chireceanu C., Teodoru A., Chiriloiu A. 2017 New Records of the Oak Lace Bug *Corythucha arcuata* (Say, 1832) (Hemiptera: Tingidae) in Southern Romania. *Acta zoologica bulgarica Suppl.* 9: 297-299.
- Csepelényi M., Hirka A., Szénási Á., Mikó Á., Szöcs L., Csóka G. 2017a Rapid area expansion and mass occurrences of the invasive oak lace bug [*Corythucha arcuata* (Say 1932)] in Hungary. *Erdészettudományi Közlemények* 7 (2): 127-134. (In Hungarian, English summary).
- Csepelényi M., Hirka A., Mikó Á., Szalai Á., Csóka Gy. 2017b Overwintering success of the oak lace bug (*Corythucha arcuata*) in 2016/2017 at South-eastern Hungary. *Növényvédelem* 78 (53) 7: 285-288.
- Dobрева M., Simov N., Georgiev G., Mirchev P., Georgieva M. 2013 First Record of *Corythucha arcuata* (Say) (Heteroptera: Tingidae) on Balkan Peninsula. *Acta zoologica bulgarica* 65 (3): 409-412.
- Forster B., Giacalone I., Moretti M., Dioli P., Wermelinger B. 2005 Die amerikanische Eichennetzwanze *Corythucha arcuata* (Say) (Heteroptera, Tingidae) hat die Südschweiz erreicht. *Mitteilungen der Schweizerischen Entomologischen Gesellschaft* 78: 317-323.
- Georgiev G., Tsankov G., Mirchev P., Petkov P., Todorov M. 2008 Honeydew producers in oak forests of Strandzha Mountain, Bulgaria. *Silva Balcanica* 9 (1): 85-90.
- Georgiev G., Georgieva M., Mirchev P., Zhiyanski M. 2017 Main insect pests and fungal pathogens on tree and shrub vegetation in urban ecosystems. Hlorind Ltd., Sofia, 54 pp.
- Georgieva M., Zlatanov Ts., Petkov P., Rosnev B., Georgiev G., Mirchev P. 2013 Effect of *Cryphonectria parasitica* (Murrill.) Barr. on the health condition of chestnut (*Castanea sativa* Mill.) on the northern slopes of Belasitsa Mountain. *Forest Science* 1 (2): 73-87. (In Bulgarian, English summary)
- Hrašovec B., Posarić D., Lukić I., Pernek M. 2013 First record of oak lace bug (*Corythucha arcuata*) in Croatia. *Šumarski list* 137 (9-10): 499-503.
- Jurc M., Jurc D. 2017 The first record and the beginning the spread of oak lace bug, *Corythucha arcuata* (Say, 1832) (Heteroptera: Tingidae) in Slovenia. *Šumarski list* 141 (9-10): 485-488.
- Küçükbasmacı İ. 2014 Two new invasive species recorded in Kastamonu (Turkey): Oak lace bug [*Corythucha arcuata* (Say, 1832)] and sycamore lace bug [*Corythucha ciliata* (Say, 1832)] (Heteroptera: Tingidae). *Journal of Entomology and Nematology* 6 (8): 104-111. DOI: 10.5897/JEN2014.0102.
- Mutun S. 2003 First report of the oak lace bug, *Corythucha arcuata* (Say, 1832) (Heteroptera: Tingidae) from Bolu, Turkey. *Israel Journal of Zoology* 49: 323-324.
- Mutun S., Ceyhan Z., Sözen C. 2009 Invasion by the Oak Lace Bug, *Corythucha arcuata* (Say) (Heteroptera: Tingidae), in Turkey. *Turkish Journal of Zoology* 33 (3): 263-268.
- Neimorovets V., Shchurov V., Bondarenko A., Skvortsov M., Konstantinov F. 2017 First Documented Outbreak and New Data on the Distribution of *Corythucha arcuata* (Say, 1832) (Hemiptera: Tingidae) in Russia. *Acta zoologica bulgarica Suppl.* 9: 139-142.
- Nikl P. 2017 Pests of urban trees in Botanical garden Faculty of science Zagreb in year 2016. *Preddiplomski studij, Urbano šumarstvo, zaštita prirode i okoliša, Zagreb*, 28 pp.
- Pap P., Drekić M., Poljaković-Pajnik L., Marković M., Vasić V. 2015. Forest health monitoring in Vojvodina in 2015. *Topola* 195/196: 117-133.
- Simov N., Langourov M., Grozeva S., Gradinarov D. 2012 New and Interesting Records of Alien and Native True Bugs (Hemiptera: Heteroptera) in Bulgaria. *Acta zoologica bulgarica* 64 (3): 241-252.